

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Dental health among 15 year old children from Strumica city in South-Eastern part of Republic of Macedonia

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The aim of this study was to assess dental caries in 15-year-old children attending regular public secondary school in Strumica.

Methods: The study was conducted during 2013 year for adolescents aged 15. In this cross-sectional study, secondary school children from first grades [n=545] were selected from two Secondary Schools in Strumica. Participants dental status was evaluated using the 1997 World Health Organization caries diagnostic criteria for Decayed, Missing or Filled Teeth [DMFT] by 2 calibrated examiners. P value ≤0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The total number of children in the sample was 545, comprising 206 [37.80%] females and 339 [62.20%] males. The mean DMFT was 3.36, with standard deviation [SD] of 2.99 and 95% confidence interval [CI] of 3.11-3.61. Significant caries [SiC] index was 6.69. The prevalence of caries-free children was 19.08 %. The percentage of untreated caries or the ration of DT/DMFT was 0.4386 [43.86%].

Conclusions: Dental caries experience was seen to be moderate among secondary school children from Strumica city and its surrounding.

Keywords: Caries; Caries prevalence; DMFT index; Macedonia; School children.

INTRODUCTION

Oral diseases are among the most common chronic diseases worldwide and they not only have an impact on general health and quality of life but may also increase the risk of mortality [1]. Since 1938, the DMF index has become a relevant tool in monitoring of distribution trends concerning dental caries; applied by the WHO in their assessment of oral health, reflecting the intensity or frequency of dental caries [2].

Several authors have previously emphasized that caries is an illness by a number of factors and that one

specific method for its assessment, which includes all of the factors, of caries etiology, does not exist [3]. These factors include the consumption of sugar and sugar-containing foods [4], plaque [5], inflammation of the gums, high salivary counts of *Streptococcus mutans* in the children and mothers [6], and the parents' attitude towards health [7].

Demographic characteristics have been considered to explain the differences in caries occurrence. Age is one such factor and higher caries prevalence with increasing age has been demonstrated [8-11]. In addition, children with caries with caries disease at an early age were likely

to develop new lesion later [12, 13]. Our study assessed the dental caries experience among adolescents living in Strumica city and different villages around Strumica city, in the South-Eastern region of the Republic of Macedonia.

METHODS

The sample for the present cross-sectional study was 545 secondary school children from first grades, attending two public secondary schools in Strumica city. Permission for the study was obtained from the school authorities, who sought and obtained consent from the parents of the children concerned.

It was decided to use cluster sampling because it was more economical and achievable within the constraints of resources and finance. All classes (first grades) students in these two schools were included in the study. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ministry of Health. Students from first grades of secondary schools are around 15 years old, and at this age the permanent teeth have been exposed to the oral environment for 3-9 years. The assessment of caries prevalence is therefore often more meaningful than at 12 years of age.

Data were collected by means of clinical examinations in daylight using plain dental mirrors and probe, which took place in a separate room within PHO Health Center-Strumica. Two calibrated dental examiners conducted the dental examination and the clinical part of the form was filled in by two other trained dentists [kappa values for inter-examiner reliability was 0.85]. World Health Organization 2013 [14], caries diagnostic criteria were followed. The DMFT, Decayed, Missed, or Filled Teeth (DMFT) and SiC indices were used to evaluate students dental caries experience. A new index called the 'Significant Caries Index' (SiC) was recently proposed by the World Health Organization (WHO) to draw attention to those individuals with the highest caries scores in each population [15]. The SiC Index leads to significant gains for society and for the persons concerned as more specific targeted preventive actions can be implemented. The SiC is the mean DMFT of one third of the study group with the highest caries score.

Statistical analysis

Simple descriptive statistical tests were used in the form of percentage and frequency distribution. For statistical analysis of DMFT scores to assess the oral health among secondary school students, the R software environment for statistical computing was used (<http://www.r-project.org>).

RESULTS

Statistical data that was collected were from secondary school students in the Southeast part of the Republic of Macedonia. For each student following data was recorded: age, sex (male or female), ethnic group, area (urban or rural), city/village, number of Decayed Teeth (DT), number of Missing Teeth (MT) and number of Filled Teeth (FT). Then, the DMFT score, the sum of DT, MT and FT, was calculated and recorded for each student. The size of the statistical sample was 545. In Table 1, the distribution of individuals in studied sample is given.

The mean value of the DMFT index for the whole sample is 3.36, with Standard Deviation (SD) of 2.99 and 95% Confidence Interval (CI) of 3.11-3.62. In the whole sample, 19.08% of the individuals were caries free (DMFT=0). As a complement of the mean DMFT value, for the whole sample, the SiC index of 6.69 was calculated.

In figure 1, the distribution of DMFT score is given. The Shapiro-Wilk test for normality was performed, and the hypothesis that the data is normally distributed is rejected with p-value $2.2e-16 < 0.05$. In figure 2 the boxplot of DMFT score in the whole sample is given, showing the range, quartiles and outliers. The mean DMFT index with SD and 95% CI were calculated for each group (according to gender, area of living and living in city or village) and these results are reported in Table 2. If there are p-values that are less than 0.05, the differences among groups are considered to be statistically significant (between: males and females, individuals who live in urban and rural area, individuals who live in different city/village).

Table 1. Distribution of individuals in studied sample (gender, area).

Area	Sex		Total
	Female	Male	
Urban	134 (24,59%)	120 (22,02%)	192 (35,23%)
Rural	72 (13,21%)	219 (40,18%)	353 (64,77%)
Total	206 (37,80%)	339 (62,20%)	545 (100%)

Table 2. Caries free individuals, DMFT scores and equality tests for mean DMFT index.

SiC	Caries free	DMFT		p-value	
		Mean (SD)	95% CI		
whole sample	6.69	104 (19.08%)	3.36 (2.99)	3.11-3.62	
sex groups					
male	6.23	77 (22.71%)	3.04 (2.90)	2.73-3.35	p<0.05
female	7.52	27 (13.11%)	3.88 (3.08)	3.46-4.31	
area groups					
urban area	7.58	33 (17.19%)	3.81 (3.40)	3.33-4.30	p< 0.05
rural area	6.15	71 (20.11%)	3.12 (2.72)	2.83-3.40	

Figure 1. Distribution of DMFT score in the whole sample.

In Table 2, the percentage of caries free individuals for each group is also reported. Distributions of DMFT scores for some of the groups are illustrated by the boxplots (Figures 4-6).

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA): p -value = $0.001628 < 0.05$, which means that there is statistically significant differences between mean DMFT scores for males and females. Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test (this is a nonparametric test, so the normality of data is not necessary, the equality of medians is tested, and it achieves its best performance for sample sizes 5 and larger): p -value = $0.0007158 < 0.05$, which means that there is statistically significant differences between DMFT medians for males and females.

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA): p -value = $0.01560 < 0.05$, which means that there is statistically significant differences between mean DMFT scores for individuals who live in urban and rural area. Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test [this is a nonparametric test, so the normality of data is not necessary, the equality of medians is tested, and it achieves its best performance for sample sizes 5 and larger]: p -value = $0.03539 < 0.05$, which means that there is statistically significant differences between DMFT medians for individuals who live in urban and rural area.

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test (this is a nonparametric test, so the normality of data is not necessary, the equality of medians is tested, and it achieves its best performance for sample sizes 5 and larger): p -value = $0.01108 < 0.05$, which means that there is statistically significant differences between DMFT medians for individuals who live in different city/village (with 5 and more individuals in studied sample).

The DMFT components, DT, MT and FT, were also analyzed. Their frequencies, mean values, SD's and 95% CI's are reported in Table 3. It is important to describe the composition of the DMFT, which allows us to evaluate the level of dental care in the country.

DISCUSSION

Although there is a plethora of published studies of dental caries experience among different age groups in different regions of the world, there is a lack of data on dental caries experience in the literature with regard to the Republic of Macedonia. The study aimed to assess the dental caries experience in secondary school students from the biggest city (Strumica) in the Southeast Region of the Republic of Macedonia. The purpose of the study was to help planning preventive programmes and to serve

as a baseline for future evaluation of preventive treatment for this age group.

According to the WHO Report, dental caries affects 60-90 % of schoolchildren and the vast majority of adults, indicating how massive the extent of this public health problem actually is so that it emerges in the majority of industrialized countries [16].

Today Macedonia has remained far from the objectives set by WHO for 2020 as part of the “Health 21 Policy” for Europe (on average no more than 1.5 DMF should be observed in 12-year-olds and at least 80 % of 6-year-olds should be caries free) [17, 18].

Figure 2. Boxplot of DMFT score in the whole sample.

Figure 3. Boxplots of DT, MT and FT score in the whole sample.

Figure 4. Boxplots of DMFT score for sex groups.

Figure 5. Boxplots of DMFT score for area groups.

Table 3. DT, MT, FT frequencies and scores for the whole sample

	Frequency	Mean [SD]	95% CI
DT	43.86%	1.48 [2.19]	1.29-1.66
MT	8.57%	0.29 [0.71]	0.23-0.35
FT	47.57%	1.60 [2.36]	1.40-1.80

However, according to the results given by Ambarkova et al. [19] in 2014, mean DMFT value was acquired in the 12-year children from East region of our country. Because we know that DMFT score increases with increasing age, we expected that the 15-year group of children from South-eastern region will have higher DMFT scores than 12-year old children.

The results of another study in Montenegro show an increase in caries prevalence with age. Thus, 91% of 12 year olds have one or more carious lesions with a maximum value 97% among 15-year olds and 98% among children 18 years of age, while the average DMF index in 12-year olds is 4.4, within 15-year olds is 8.25 and within 18-year olds is 10.9 [20].

All official data on dental caries, on the national level in the Republic of Macedonia (Department of Dental Health at the Ministry of Health), and on the international level (World Health Organization, WHO), register dental caries only when manifested as cavity while initial caries lesion is not registered [21].

The Omission of the registration of initial carious lesions can lead to an underestimation of the total decay in the population [22-24]. In order to improve oral health in the Republic of Macedonia adopted the National Strategy for Prevention of oral diseases in children 0-14

years, from 2008 to 2018 [25]. In it as primary preventive measures were included mechanical and chemical control of dental plaque, endogenous and exogenous application of fluoride, controlled intake of sugars, regular dental care, the use of dental floss, sealing of fissure, education and motivation for maintaining oral health. For the implementation of this program as a professional staff, all pediatric and preventive dentistry specialists and general dentists who are employed in the state preventive dentistry sector and also educators in kindergartens and teachers in schools are involve.

In Macedonia there is an inadequate system for monitoring and recording of dental caries, whose statistics is not harmonized with that of the European Union and WHO, existing legal obligations are not respected and therefore there is no relevant statistical indicators (DMFT) [26, 27].

Figure 6. Boxplots of DMFT score for city/village groups.

The results of the scientific project “Oral health condition and rehabilitation needs of the population” of our country, derived from epidemiological study conducted in 1991 and made under the common Yugoslav study “Assessment of oral health and necessary treatment in populations of Yugoslavia, applying the basic criteria initiative of the WHO”, indicate a very serious condition. DMF index ranged from 0.54 within the six-year children upon 23.84 DMFT index within the population over 65 years old. This study directed by Necheva and conducted in the cities of Skopje, Veles, Stip and Ohrid, covered 1,034 subjects from rural and urban population groups aged 6, 12, 15, 18, 35-44 and over 65 from the whole Republic were examined. High values of DMF index were registered in all the age groups, with prevalence in the children groups, among

permanent teeth. The average DMF score for 15 year olds was 8.13 [28]. Within 15 year old adolescents the lowest value of the average DMF index is determined in Veles, while it is almost equal in Ohrid (11.54) and Skopje (10.08) [28, 29].

In the previous our studies, the intensity of dental caries in 15 year olds from the East region is high [10], within 15-year old adolescents from the Vardar region is moderate [8], while within the adolescents of the same age from the Southeast region is also moderate.

The results of our previous studies [8, 10], indicate poor oral health of 15-year olds from the Eastern and the Vardar region, according to our interpretation, due to inadequately organized dental service which existed in the past, inadequate dental personnel deployed, unplanned work and, as most important the absence of a

planned and organized prevention activities. It can be concluded from the fact that in the Vardar region there are only nine, in the Eastern seven, while in the Southern region eight Specialists Dentist for Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry, while in the Skopje (Capital) region there are 35 Specialists Dentist for Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry.

SiC index was introduced in order to focus attention on individuals with a high score of cavities in each population. Strategic goal of a country SiC index is less than the value of DMFT 3 children 12 years of age [30]. The school time is a period when lasting habits occur and when health educational measures are of the greatest benefit. Children must be persuaded that the mouth and the teeth are the mirror of the health and that there is no full health without the oral health [31]. Wennhall I et al. showed that the adjusted preventive programs pre-school children living in a multicultural society with low socio-economic development are cost effective and of great advantage for society and of great benefit to the individual [32]. Dental caries is still an urgent problem among children [23].

A major turning point in targeting of the population with high caries risk occurs with the introduction of the Significant Caries Index (SiC) which covers individuals subgroups with the highest caries scores. With its introduction the World Health Organization makes a great step forward in the introduction of the new global order in the area of oral health, such as the value of the Significant Caries Index till 2015 to be less than three [30, 33, 34].

The overall mean DMFT was 3.36 and this can be classified as moderate dental caries experience. Moreover, the DMFT index was 3.36 and the SiC 6.69, indicating that one-third of the sample had a caries experience twice the mean DMFT.

There was gender difference in the mean DMFT and the prevalence of caries-free 15-year olds in Strumica city was higher in male (22.71%), than female (13.11%). The ratio of DT/DMFT gives an indication of treatment need. In the current study, this ratio indicated that untreated caries was responsible for 0.04386 (43.86%) of the DMFT index. It was clear that almost half of the caries experience was untreated, indicating that there was a problem with access to dental care service by this age group.

It should be noted that it is not appropriate to make a direct comparison of the DMF scores among individual European countries because of different methodologies and different periods used to obtain the data [35]. Also, it is well known that numerous socioeconomic and demographic factors have an impact on the oral status and dental caries prevalence such as age, gender, urbanization, economic conditions and other [36, 37].

All the above-mentioned data show evidently that it is necessary to intensify actions of control and promotion of oral health in Macedonia. In July 2007, the Ministry of Health adopted the “National strategy for prevention of oral diseases in children from 0 to 14 years of age in the Republic of Macedonia for the period from 2008 to 2018” as a key document setting the priorities of dental health care [25].

Sweden, Norway and Denmark are examples of countries that have begun to collect DMF data at national level through public dental health care programmes. They have developed and continue to develop valuable systems to improve the quality of data and identify indicators of quality in dental health care [38].

A group of experts from all around the world in 2010, formed the Alliance for the future without caries (ACFF) to promote integrated clinical and public health plans that will lead to a reduction in the prevalence of dental caries globally by improving information acquisition healthy lifestyles, based on behavioral change [39].

Long has been known fact that the lack of regular oral hygiene habits play a significant role in the development of the cavities. Children oral health can be influenced by the parents attitudes and behavior on oral health, as well as their own oral health [40-42].

The main advantage of this study is that it, was performed using internationally accepted methodology recommended by the WHO (2013) [14] allowing comparability of the findings with European studies and with earlier studies in the region. The limitations of the DMFT index for epidemiological use have been discussed in many articles [43-47]. It is claimed that it mixes disease and treatment and makes it difficult to differentiate between previous or existing caries. The index is irreversible and cannot inform whether restorations (filled teeth F), are due to caries or other reasons, e.g. hypoplasia. The “filled teeth (F)” criterion is also inaccurate as the criteria behind the decision of a practitioner to fill a tooth, are undefined. Another problem is that the DMFT index does not indicate whether the caries lesion reported is in an active or inactive state (arrested caries). It is additionally impossible to consider the number of teeth that are at risk of caries and it cannot monitor caries progression. Another limitation is that we did not use the ICDAS system which gives more detailed description on the severity of caries.

According to Krisdapong et al. [46], the traditional method of measuring oral health and treatment needs, based principally on clinical indices, is inadequate [7, 12]. He tough that to better comprehend a population’s oral health and consequently plan oral health services more appropriately, some countries have included

measures of perceived oral health or OHRQoL in their national oral health surveys [32, 44, 46-49].

Fluoride tablets are also available on our market, but despite being on the positive list of drugs, they are not prescribed regularly enough for children with high caries risk profile and active caries in children by dentists, gynecologists and pediatricians. Fluoride gels and varnishes for professional use contain high levels of fluoride, but because of the process of privatization of dentistry, private dentists do not pay enough attention to this preventive measure so that its benefit is lacking. They need to be applied in children with high caries risk and it is a highly controlled process by pediatric dentists where the child is treated.

The high incidence of the most frequent oral diseases such as dental caries, gingival inflammation and periodontal disease have imposed the need for adoption of strategic plan for the organization and reform of oral health care in which the vision and the goals for the development of modern, effective and rational health are clearly defined.

According to the assessments of many national and international experts, that type of activities involves establishing of an integrated health care protection with mandatory control of the quality, as well as responsible management of the available resources, according to WHO recommendations, which are incorporated in the principles of the European Union, where the main priority is the preservation of oral health.

Along these lines, Republic of Macedonia also needs to continue and intensify efforts towards further development of the system of oral-health monitoring and protection, in compliance with appropriate quality standards, through cooperation of numerous participants such as the Ministry of Health, the Macedonian Institute of Public Health, the Macedonian Health Insurance Fund, the schools of dental medicine and providers of dental health care, all with the aim to achieve the anticipated results.

CONCLUSIONS

The DMF index data in adolescents from Strumica city show that dental caries is still a public health problem indicating that actions must be taken at national and local level. The establishment of dental health and DMF index databases and the appropriate understanding of factors that lead to occurrence of dental caries are important for objectives to be set and preventive programmes to be planned in the domain of oral health.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

VA: data collection, interpretation, writing and study design. VP: data collection. The final manuscript has been read and approved by both authors.

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